

Abstract

Despite the ecological importance of marine pico-size eukaryotes, the study of their *in situ* diversity using molecular tools started just a few years ago. These studies have revealed that
25 marine picoeukaryotes are very diverse and include many novel taxa. However, the amount and structure of their phylogenetic diversity and the extent of their sequence novelty still remains poorly known, since a systematic analysis has been seldom attempted. Here we use a coherent and carefully curated dataset of 500 published 18S rDNA sequences to quantify the diversity and novelty patterns of picoeukaryotes in the Indian Ocean. Our phylogenetic tree
30 showed that seawater was populated by many distantly related evolutionary units. We grouped sequences in OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) at discrete values delineated by pair-wise Jukes-Cantor distances or tree patristic distances. Half of the sequences grouped at 0.01 distance (237/242 OTUs observed), indicating the existence of microdiverse clusters of highly related sequences. Using such a low distance we estimated 731/803 OTUs. The
35 number of OTUs observed was still substantial at high distance levels (94/121 at 0.10 distance; 39/82 at 0.20 distance) suggesting a large diversity of high-taxonomic ranks. Most sequences were related to marine clones from other sites and many were distant to cultured organisms, highlighting the huge culturing gap within protists. The novelty analysis also indicated the putative presence of pseudogenes and of truly novel high-rank phylogenetic
40 lineages. The found diversity and novelty patterns among marine picoeukaryotes are of great importance for understanding and interpreting their ecology and evolution.

Keywords: diversity / genetic distances / microdiversity / novelty / OTUs / picoeukaryotes

45 **Introduction**

Planktonic protists play fundamental roles in the functioning of marine ecosystems, both as primary producers and microbial grazers (Sherr *et al.*, 2007). Their diversity has since long attracted marine biologists, which were surprised that a seemingly homogeneous habitat with a limited range of resources could sustain the high diversity observed. This phenomenon was
50 named the paradox of the plankton (Hutchinson, 1961). Today it is assumed that biological and environmental factors interact continually, so the plankton habitat never reaches an equilibrium, preventing competitive exclusion by a single species and promoting diversity (Scheffer *et al.*, 2003). Little was known for the smallest protists (picoeukaryotes, cells of 0.8-3 μm), which are hardly visible by inverted microscopy. Epifluorescence and flow cytometry
55 counts (Johnson and Sieburth, 1982; Olson *et al.*, 1985) revealed their abundance, ubiquity, and ecological relevance, but still did not allow identification. This was made possible with the introduction of molecular tools to oceanography that provided a culturing and microscopic independent assessment of microbial diversity (Giovannoni *et al.*, 1990). A series of seminal studies showed that marine picoeukaryotes were indeed very diverse, similar to what was
60 observed for larger protists, and contained many novel lineages (Diez *et al.*, 2001; Moon-van der Staay *et al.*, 2001; López-García *et al.*, 2001). Comparable patterns were also observed in the first freshwater molecular surveys (Lefranc *et al.*, 2005; Richards *et al.*, 2005).

The methodological improvements to retrieve phylogenetically informative genes from the environment have been paralleled by a growing understanding of the eukaryotic tree of life
65 based on cultured organisms. The most recent phylogenomic data identifies the same lineages as cell ultrastructure studies and unites lineages with disparate morphologies but common evolutionary origins into a few supergroups. The eukaryotic tree of life was first delineated with eight supergroups (Baldauf, 2003), which have been further reduced to six (Simpson and

Roger, 2004), or less (Burki *et al.*, 2008). Examples are the stramenopiles, which include
70 diatoms, chrysophytes and bicosoecids, or the opisthokonts, which include choanoflagellates,
fungi and metazoans. The eukaryotic tree of life represents an optimal framework to assign
environmental sequences to known lineages or to define new ones if environmental sequences
do not find a place. Thus, novel groups such as marine stramenopiles (MAST, Massana *et al.*,
2004), marine alveolates (MALV, Guillou *et al.*, 2008), or picobiliphytes (Not *et al.*, 2007)
75 have been defined based on environmental surveys. They represent previously unnoticed but
ubiquitous marine grazers, parasites and algae, respectively.

Despite the numerous molecular surveys of marine picoeukaryotes (reviewed in Massana and
Pedrós-Alió, 2008; Vaulot *et al.*, 2008), the knowledge about the extent of their diversity at
different phylogenetic scales and the pattern of sequence novelty is still in its infancy. Few
80 studies have reported the number of lineages observed grouping sequences at different
clustering levels (Caron *et al.*, 2009). Parametric and non-parametric statistics have been used
to estimate the total richness in different habitats, including picoeukaryotes from the marine
plankton (Brown *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, little has been advanced in quantifying and
representing the novelty patterns of sequences from environmental surveys. Here we are
85 addressing these issues by using a coherent and curated dataset of environmental sequences of
picoeukaryotes (500 sequences of ~800 bp). These sequences were published as part of a
general study of small protists in the Indian Ocean (Not *et al.*, 2008) and the analysis we
present here is totally new. Specific questions are: How many described taxonomic groups are
detected? How many OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) are observed when clustering
90 sequences at different thresholds? Is the clustering method affecting the previous view? How
many OTUs can be estimated? What is the novelty pattern of environmental sequences? Our
study is an effort to describe the diversity and novelty of marine picoeukaryotes exploiting the
data gathered in a classical 18S rDNA clone library approach, in order to set up a baseline in

which to compare the massive amount of data that are just beginning to be available by high-
95 throughput sequencing (Amaral-Zettler *et al.*, 2009; Brown *et al.*, 2009).

Material and Methods

Sequence dataset

Sequences derive from a recent study (Not *et al.*, 2008). Eight clone libraries of the 18S
100 rDNA genes from the picoplankton (0.2 to 3 μm) were prepared from surface and Deep
Chlorophyll Maximum samples collected at four stations in the Indian Ocean. One station was
coastal, whereas the other three stations (representing 91% of the sequences) were offshore.
Details of DNA extraction, PCR (with eukaryotic primers EukA and EukB) and cloning
protocols can be found in the original publication. Clones were sequenced with the internal
105 primer 528f, resulting in 572 sequences of around 850 bp. The taxonomic affiliation of each
sequence (including chimera detection) was done by BLAST (Altschul *et al.*, 1997) and
KeyDNATools (<http://www.keydnatools.com/>) searches and comparison with published
phylogenetic trees. A final dataset of 500 protist sequences was obtained after excluding 30
metazoan sequences, 33 chimeras, and 9 sequences shorter than 500 bp or of low quality. All
110 chromatograms were visually inspected to minimize sequencing errors.

Phylogenetic analysis

Sequences were aligned with MAFFT using the slow and iterative refinement method FFT-
NS-i (Kato *et al.*, 2002). The alignment was edited with Seaview 3.2 (Galtier *et al.*, 1996) to
keep the longest region common in most sequences. The final alignment had 961 positions
115 and ~815 bp per sequence (the average size was 797 bp, indicating that most positions in the
alignment were covered). Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic trees were constructed

with RAxML (Stamatakis, 2006) using the evolutionary model GTR+G+I that best fits our data following ModelTest (Posada and Crandall, 1998). Phylogenetic analyses were done in the freely available University of Oslo Bioportal (www.bioportal.uio.no). Repeated runs on
120 distinct starting trees were carried out to select the tree with the best topology (the one having the best Likelihood of 1000 alternative trees). Bootstrap ML analysis was done with 1000 pseudo-replicates. Trees were edited with the online tool iTOL (Letunic and Bork, 2007).

Grouping sequences in OTUs

Pair-wise Jukes-Cantor (JC) distances among all sequences were computed with PAUP
125 (Swofford, 2002) after an alignment with unique sequences (398 sequences). The distance matrix was processed with DOTUR (Schloss and Handelsman, 2005) to group sequences in OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) at different clustering distances. We used the rule of furthest neighbor and the highest precision ($p=10000$). Heatmaps and Venn diagrams comparing samples were obtained from the related application Mothur. OTUs were also
130 delineated with the online tool RAMI (Pommier *et al.*, 2009), which grouped sequences based on their patristic distances (branch lengths). Rarefaction analysis were performed on both DOTUR and RAMI applications using the alignment with all 500 sequences.

Estimating the total number of OTUs

The total number of OTUs (defined at discrete clustering levels) was estimated applying a set
135 of statistical models to the observed OTU abundance. Parametric methods apply a model to the frequency distribution of OTUs and then project the distribution to estimate how many OTUs have been missed (Jeon *et al.*, 2006), whereas non-parametric methods such as Chao1 or ACE just apply a simple equation (Chao and Lee, 1992). Several parametric and non-parametric estimators (under different competing models and assumptions) were run at every
140 possible right-truncation point of the frequency-count data, i.e., omitting outliers (highly

abundant taxa in the sample) with the beta version of the program CatchAll built at the Department of Statistical Science, Cornell University. The best parametric model was selected as the one providing the best compromise with a high goodness of fit, low standard error, and maximal use of large frequency counts. The non-parametric model was chosen
145 based on the coefficient of variation of the estimate (Shen *et al.*, 2003).

Novelty analysis

Two values were recorded after BLASTing each environmental sequence against the nucleotide collection (nr/nt) database of NCBI (search on March 2010). The first value was the similarity with the closest environmental sequence in the BLAST output list (Similarity
150 CEM [Closest Environmental Match]), excluding clones from the same library or study. The second was the similarity with the closest cultured organism (Similarity CCM [Closest Cultured Match]), which was the first entry in the list that was taxonomically classified. In a few cases, environmental sequences were so divergent that BLAST calculated the similarity using only a fragment, overestimating the similarity value. This occurred in 21 cases with the
155 CEM and 38 cases with the CCM. In these instances, environmental and GenBank sequences were aligned with MAFFT, and the similarity was calculated after the uncorrected p-distance computed in PAUP. The novelty analysis reported the similarities of the environmental sequences against CEM and CCM in histograms or in dispersion plots (del Campo and Massana, submitted).

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Results

Phylogenetic reconstruction of the diversity of marine picoeukaryotes

The picoeukaryote diversity from the Indian Ocean was evidenced in our maximum
165 likelihood phylogenetic tree including all 500 sequences (Figure 1). In this tree, colored
branches and external rings are based on a taxon-assignment of sequences after BLAST and
KeyDNATools. Both independent approaches, tree phylogeny and sequence assignment, were
remarkably concordant (Figure 1a). The main supergroups (inner ring) were well represented
and were divided into taxonomic groups roughly at the Class level (outer ring), most of them
170 with high bootstrap values. Alveolates (darkest gray in the inner ring) accounted for most
clones in the dataset, in particular dinoflagellates, MALV-I and MALV-II (47% of clones).
Stramenopiles (light gray) were formed by several lineages at moderate clonal abundance
(19% of clones), being MAST groups the most represented, followed by chrysophytes and
bicosoecids. Rhizaria (medium gray) were formed mostly by radiolarians (13% of clones).
175 The two cercozoan sequences were wrongly placed, being closer to ciliates than radiolarians.
Archaeplastida (lightest gray) were formed exclusively by prasinophytes and accounted for
4% of clones. The remaining groups (green in the inner ring) contained few badly resolved
sequences. They affiliated with typical marine groups such as haptophytes, cryptophytes,
katablepharids, picobiliphytes, telonemida and choanoflagellates. The same tree with real
180 branch lengths (Figure 1b) gave a general impression of the unequal variability contained in
each taxonomic group.

This highly supported tree was pivotal to place very divergent sequences that could not be
identified after BLAST and KeyDNATools searches (21 sequences shown in light green
branches). These novel sequences showed very long branches in the tree (Figure 1b) and,
185 interestingly, some affiliated within a given taxonomic group. Thus, two divergent sequences
were related to MALV-II, one to cercozoans, two to picobiliphytes and one to MAST (the
three first cases supported by high bootstrap values). Nevertheless, fifteen novel sequences

could still not be related to any taxonomic group not even to a supergroup and appeared somehow related at the root of the tree.

190 *Number of OTUs observed at varying clustering distances*

Identical sequences were removed resulting in 398 unique sequences that represented the number of OTUs at null distance. Unique sequences were then grouped into OTUs at distinct thresholds based on JC pair-wise distances or patristic distances displayed in the ML tree. The number of OTUs showed the largest decrease with the initial clustering relaxation (Figure 2a).

195 Thus, the initial 398 OTUs were reduced to 237/242 at 0.01 distance (equivalent to 99% similarity; Figure 2a), meaning that 40% of the unique sequences collapse at this low distance (Figure 2b). After this dramatic initial decline, the number of OTUs continuously decrease when increasing the clustering distance. JC and patristic distances grouped OTUs similarly up to a distance of 0.10, and above this value patristic distances delineated more OTUs (Figure
200 2a). This could not be caused by the evolution model, since pair-wise JC and ML distances gave similar values (slope=1.0253; $R^2=0.9993$; 500 sequences). Instead, these differences seem to appear due to the accumulative information gathered when constructing the ML tree. For instance, at a distance of 0.20 roughly separating taxonomic Classes, JC distances delineate 39 OTUs whereas patristic distances delineated 82. These differences are also
205 evident in the distribution of OTUs in distance classes (Figure 2b).

Rarefaction curves were then constructed to relate the number of OTUs with the sequencing effort. The rarefaction curve with OTUs grouped at null JC distance did not show any sign of saturation (Figure 2c). Rarefaction curves done with OTUs clustered at increasing distances showed a progressively better coverage, with plateaus starting to be evident at levels of 0.2
210 and 0.3 for both grouping methods. This indicated a severe undersampling to retrieve OTUs

defined stringently, but at the same time suggested that the higher-rank phylogenetic groups were moderately well represented in the sequence dataset.

Our dataset included a huge sequence variability (Figure 1b) and raised doubts about the accuracy of the alignment used for calculating pair-wise distances and the ML tree. In addition, hypervariable regions, kept to report the variability at all scales, were inevitably ambiguously aligned. Thus, we expected that doing separate analysis for coherent phylogenetic groups would yield better OTU counts. We prepared sequence datasets with the taxonomic groups shown in Figure 1a and redid the OTU counting (alignment, JC distances and DOTUR) for the 23 separate sets. Then, the number of OTUs in each set were added up and compared with the number observed with the whole dataset. To our surprise, both approaches gave similar OTU numbers at clustering distance levels up to 0.30, being almost identical at all levels tested up to 0.10 (Figure 3). This exercise sustains the accuracy of the OTU counts and the ML tree obtained using the whole, and very variable, dataset.

Number of OTUs estimated at varying clustering distances

The rarefaction curves clearly showed that our dataset underestimated diversity, particularly when OTUs were defined at low genetic distances. In order to estimate the "total" number of OTUs, we applied several statistical models on their frequency distribution (Table 1). Parametric methods tend to predict higher estimates than nonparametric methods, and this was also observed here. The best parametric estimate obtained at null distance was 1951 (\pm 193), and a distance of 0.01 was 731 (\pm 150) or 803 (\pm 188). OTU estimates at increasing distances decrease parallel to the decrease in the observed number, although observed and estimated values get closer at high distances. So, whereas at 0.01 the observed OTUs represent 32-30% of the estimated value, at 0.20 they represent 63-51% (Table 1). So we are missing many more low-rank taxa than high-rank lineages.

For each sequence, the similarity against the closest environmental match (CEM) and the closest cultured match (CCM) was recorded. The average CEM similarity (97.9%) was much higher than the average CCM similarity (91.9%). The similarity distribution against CEM was skewed towards the highest values, with a marked peak at 99%, whereas CCM similarity distributed well from 85% to 100%, with minor peaks at 87%, 92% and 99% (Figure 4a). A dispersion plot of both similarity values showed that few sequences were closer to CCM than to CEM, with most dots at the 1:1 line or below (Figure 4b). A notable exception were ten sequences close to *Amastigomonas debrynei* but only 80% similar to a marine clone. Dots were colored depending the neighbors they have, unveiling two dense areas (Figure 4b). The first was limited by CEM and CCM similarities above 98% (17% of sequences) and included sequences close to cultured organisms and marine clones. The second dense area was limited by CEM scores above 98% and CCM similarities between 87 and 93% (42% of sequences) and included sequences close to marine clones but distant to cultured organisms. The plot also highlighted novel sequences. Dots below 80% similarity in both axis indicated very divergent sequences never found before. Some sequences were only 75% similar with all sequences in GenBank except a few marine clones. Thus, three related clones were 98% similar to a single sequence from the Mediterranean Sea, whereas three other clones were 95-99% similar to a few Sargasso and Mediterranean Seas sequences.

Each particular phylogenetic group might exhibit a different novelty pattern, as exemplified with the supergroups alveolates and stramenopiles (Figure 5). In both cases most sequences placed in the area with high CEM similarities (>98%) and had a particular behavior with respect to CCM. Thus, some stramenopile groups are at the top of the graph with high CCM scores (bicosoecids, dictyochophytes, pelagophytes), chrysophytes shows an intermediate

position with 90-95% CCM similarities, whereas MASTs and thraustochytrids have CCM
260 similarities below 90% (Figure 5a). A similar distribution can be described for alveolates,
with dinoflagellates at the top of the graph, followed by MALV-III and -V at an intermediate
position, and MALV-I and -II with lowest CCM scores (Figure 5b).

Comparing the diversity among samples

The protist composition in different samples was compared after their OTU content defined at
265 0.01 distance, roughly corresponding to species, and at 0.20 distance, roughly corresponding
to a taxonomic level of Class. Data was displayed in heatmaps that quantify the pair-wise
difference among samples, and Venn diagrams that show the number of unique and shared
OTUs. At low distance, samples strongly differed among each other (Figure 6a), as expected
due to the undersampling shown in rarefaction curves and statistical estimates. Still, some
270 ecologically sound information was derived from the maps: the coastal sample was the most
different, and the closest pairs were two offshore surface samples (58 and 70) and two
offshore DCM samples (33 and 72). Venn diagrams were then done to compare coastal,
surface and DCM samples. At low distance level, only a few OTUs were shared and unique
OTUs were as high as 64% (coastal), 78% (surface) and 72% (DCM). As expected, OTUs
275 grouped at a higher distance gave a different picture (Figure 6b). Heatmaps showed a
homogenization of samples and Venn diagrams showed less unique OTUs (8% in coastal;
37% in surface; 33% in DCM), suggesting a rather coherent high-rank diversity among the
samples analyzed.

280 **Discussion**

Taxonomic groups detected

We used a dataset of five-hundred 18S rDNA sequences retrieved from the Indian Ocean to describe and quantify the diversity and novelty of surface marine picoeukaryotes. 18S rDNA sequences were not complete (they covered almost half of the gene, >800 bp), so they could
285 contain insufficient positions for sound phylogenies. Moreover, it was not clear whether an alignment including very divergent sequences could retrieve the proper relationships among them. The alignment was first used for a ML phylogenetic tree, which recovered the main supergroups and most taxonomic groups. In fact, the tree-independent sequence taxonomic affiliations (via BLAST and KeyDNATools) were concordant with the tree. Second, we
290 compared the OTU number computed from the whole alignment or by adding the values of 23 separate coherent alignments. Again, the results were satisfactory, as only minor differences were found at all clustering distances tested. These exercises indicated that MAFFT could deal with very variable sequence inputs and that our partial sequences were long enough for proper phylogenies, as was shown for bacterial 16S rDNA partial sequences (Stackebrandt
295 and Rainey, 1995). These tests add consistency to the results presented here.

The ML tree displayed a large diversity at different phylogenetic scales, pointing out that the seemingly homogeneous picoeukaryotic assemblages seen by epifluorescence microscopy or flow cytometry are formed by cells with very divergent evolutionary histories, a fact already stressed in the first molecular studies (Díez *et al.*, 2001; Moon-van der Staay *et al.*, 2001).
300 The high-rank diversity observed here, both in terms of eukaryotic supergroups detected and the presence and relative abundance of specific lineages, was typical of molecular surveys of marine picoeukaryotes (Massana and Pedrós-Alió, 2008; Vaulot *et al.*, 2008). Alveolates and stramenopiles were the most common groups. Rhizaria and archaeplastida appeared on a second level and were represented by a single lineage each. A unique choanoflagellate
305 sequence (fungi were absent) accounted for opisthokonts whereas excavates and amoebozoa were not detected. Several reasons might explain the absence (or very low abundance) of

some lineages in our libraries. First, some groups, such as many excavates, are likely unable to thrive in the marine plankton. Second, some cells could be excluded during the prefiltration step, such as larger loricated choanoflagellates (Leakey *et al.*, 2002) or particle-living
310 amoebas (Rogerson *et al.*, 2003). Third, some lineages could be too scarce to be detected (Pedrós-Alió, 2007), a concern that will be soon solved by high-throughput sequencing. Finally, some lineages could remain undetected due to inefficient DNA extraction or biased PCR amplification (Wintzingerode *et al.*, 1997). This will only be solved by modifying DNA extraction protocols and applying new universal and group-specific PCR primers.

315 *Observed and estimated richness at different clustering levels*

An important issue when quantifying the diversity of a natural assemblage is how to define the countable units. Ideally, units are biological species, which work reasonably well for macroorganisms but are impractical in the microbial world, where diversity is determined after DNA sequence data. In order to create tractable units, sequences above a given distance
320 threshold are pragmatically grouped into Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs). When done at discrete clustering levels, this provides the number of OTUs at different phylogenetic scales and yields information on the genetic structure of microbial assemblages (Acinas *et al.*, 2004; Shaw *et al.*, 2008). This analysis has seldom been done with marine picoeukaryotes (Caron *et al.*, 2009). The most stringent criteria using null distance would be supported by laboratory
325 studies that show that only strains with identical rDNA gene sequences are sexually compatible (Amato *et al.*, 2007). In our dataset, only 20% of sequences are not contributing to a new OTU at null distance, highlighting the large diversity of the dataset.

The largest decrease in OTU number occurred with the initial relaxation of the clustering conditions. This OTU collapse was caused by the presence of a substantial number of very
330 similar ($\geq 99\%$) but seldom identical sequences. This microdiversity could be explained by a

combination of methodological, biological and ecological factors. First, PCR or sequencing errors might account for part of these minute differences. In our dataset, chromatograms were visually inspected to confirm the high quality of the reads and remove ambiguous positions, so few sequencing errors would be expected. Second, the rDNA gene in eukaryotes appears typically in tandem repeats varying from a few to several thousand copies depending the taxa (Zhu *et al.*, 2005). Copies are generally homogenized by concerted evolution (Dover, 1982), but this process is not always complete and minor differences can be found within the same genome (Alverson and Kolnick, 2005). Third, in absence or low frequency of sexual reproduction, a plausible scenario for many protist species (Weisse, 2008), marine
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picoeukaryotes could suffer similar evolutionary processes as bacteria and reveal equivalent microdiverse clusters (Acinas *et al.*, 2004; Cohan, 2006). These clusters result from the balance between neutral mutations and ecological cohesive forces and would represent neutral genetic and functional diversity.

The number of OTUs kept decreasing when increasing distances. At distances up to 0.10, the grouping after JC or patristic distances showed a good correspondence, and the similarity
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(calculated after p-uncorrected distances) also fitted very well. Above 0.10, the number of OTUs deviate between both clustering methods, although the overall picture did not change. Patristic distances were systematically larger, implying that for a given clustering level more OTUs were detected after patristic distances. The high number of OTUs detected at large
350
distances results from the combination of a remarkable high-rank diversity (many taxonomic groups and supergroups) and the presence of very long branches at different positions of the tree (within well defined groups or forming novel high-rank lineages).

Comparing observed and estimated OTU values allowed evaluating the undersampling of our data. Parametric estimators are known to work better with low coverage datasets (Epstein and

355 López-García, 2008). They predicted 1951 OTUs at null distance and 731/803 OTUs at 0.01
distance. Thus, we only retrieved a glimpse of picoeukaryotic diversity (20% and 32-30%,
respectively). Increasing the clustering distance level the diversity coverage also increased
(consistent with the rarefaction analysis) meaning that we started to miss less lineages. Our
estimates ranked among the highest detected in surveys of microbial eukaryotes using clone
360 libraries. At a similarity clustering level of 99% (distance of 0.01), our estimate was higher
than the 398 OTUs from marine anoxic samples (Jeon *et al.*, 2006), 107 OTUs from
hypersaline deep samples (Alexander *et al.*, 2009), or 605 OTUs from hydrothermal vent
samples (Stoeck *et al.*, 2007). In surface marine samples, 572 OTUs were estimated at a
clustering level of 95% (Countway *et al.*, 2007), a number slightly higher to ours. The unique
365 high-throughput sequencing study with estimates from marine surface samples gave much
higher values: 56292 OTUs at 100% similarity, 9231 at 99% and 3765 at 95% (Brown *et al.*,
2009). Despite they only sequenced a very small amplicon (>50 bp) and analyzed a different
size fraction ($\leq 1.6 \mu\text{m}$), this study raised significantly the higher limit of protistan diversity.
Overall, marine picoeukaryotes appeared as very diverse assemblages.

370 *Novelty analysis of environmental sequences*

Novelty of environmental sequences was inferred after their similarity with the GenBank
database. At the time of the first eukaryotic molecular surveys, environmental sequences did
not exist, so only the similarity against the CCM could be calculated, yielding generally low
values (Díez *et al.*, 2001). This changed after years of molecular surveys and thousands of
375 deposited environmental sequences. In today studies, most marine sequences have a high
CEM score with marine clones from previous studies, whereas the CCM score often remains
still low. So, the large sequencing effort on marine picoeukaryotes was not paralleled by a
successful culturing effort, and relevant groups like MAST or MALV still remain uncultured.

Environmental sequences close to *Amastigomonas debruynei* represented an interesting case,
380 since they would qualify as a very novel lineage in the absence of this single strain. Culturing
novel protists holds the promise to fill similar gaps. Overall, our data highlighted the huge
culturing gap still existing for the dominant marine picoeukaryotes.

Our sequence analysis pointed out very divergent sequences that appeared as long branches in
the ML tree and in the area of the dispersion plot with very low CCM and/or CEM values. Six
385 of these sequences were placed in a given taxonomic group after the ML tree. Nine sequences
showed very low CCM and CEM scores, meaning that they were unique. They could be
pseudogenes (Thornhill *et al.*, 2007), and this could be confirmed after secondary structure
models. If pseudogenes, they would not have any ecological implication and would not stand
as separate biological units. Other six sequences were extremely divergent from any known
390 sequence except to a few marine clones. It is unlikely (but not impossible) that sequences
retrieved thousands of kilometers apart are pseudogenes. Instead, these could represent high-
rank novel phylogenetic lineages and are obvious candidates for further research. Retrieving
additional sequences, constructing sound phylogenies, and identifying the target cells through
FISH will settle down if they are truly novel evolutionary units.

395 *Concluding remarks*

In this study we explored the diversity and novelty patterns of marine picoeukaryotes using
18S rDNA clone libraries and Sanger sequencing. It should be pointed out that although far
from saturation, clone libraries can still provide longer sequences and of very high quality.
Our observations and the new exploratory approaches presented here can be adapted to
400 facilitate the analysis of the massive amounts of data from the Next Generation Sequencing
(NGS) technologies. We showed here that picoeukaryotes from the Indian Ocean were very
diverse at distinct phylogenetic scales. In fact, we are only seeing the tip of the iceberg of

their diversity and it is expected that NGS will allow investigating this underexplored space. Our data also indicated microdiverse clusters similar to those found in bacteria, but it is early
405 to explain them by ecological factors or by biological or methodological factors. Most sequences from the Indian Ocean were close to environmental sequences from other marine sites, indicating a widespread distribution of similar lineages, and many were far from cultured organisms, unveiling a significant culturing gap. We also highlighted putative pseudogenes and potentially novel high-rank phylogenetic lineages. From an ecological
410 perspective, our analysis opens the questions of what creates, maintains and structures the large diversity observed, and what are the functional implications of this large diversity at different scales. From an evolutionary perspective, we are faced with very divergent sequences that could account for new, unexpected and fascinating evolutionary lineages.

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530 **Figure legends**

Figure 1 Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree with 18S rDNA sequences of picoeukaryotes retrieved from the Indian Ocean. The tree was constructed with 500 sequences and ~815 bases in 961 positions. **(a)** Tree ignoring branch lengths and overlaid with colors with independent taxonomic assignments of sequences to an eukaryotic supergroup (inner ring) and to a given taxonomic group (colored branches and outer ring; names shown). Branches leading to groups with bootstrap values above 70% are marked with a red dot. **(b)** Same tree showing branch lengths, colored as before. The length of novel branches (light green) has been reduced to half. The scale bar indicates 0.2 substitutions per position.

Figure 2 (a) Number of OTUs observed after grouping the 398 unique sequences from the Indian Ocean at different clustering levels based on Jukes-Cantor or patristic distances. The correspondence between JC distance and sequence similarity is shown at the top of the graph for comparative purposes. **(b)** Distribution of the number of OTUs in distance classes for both grouping approaches. The area in each class represents the difference in OTUs observed at the two limits of the class (so the OTUs decrease when relaxing the clustering conditions between the two limits). **(c)** Rarefaction curves (OTUs observed versus clones analyzed) at discrete clustering distance levels (from 0.00 to 0.30) for both grouping approaches.

Figure 3 Percentage of total OTUs (estimated with the whole dataset) that are recovered in 23 analyses with defined phylogenetic groups and adding up the counts for each separate group. This comparison was done at 22 discrete clustering distance levels.

550 **Figure 4** Novelty analysis of the 500 sequences of picoeukaryotes retrieved from the Indian Ocean. **(a)** Histogram showing the distribution of similarities against Closest Environmental Match (CEM) and Closest Cultured Match (CCM) of all sequences, in 0.5% similarity

classes. **(b)** Dispersion plot of the CEM and CCM similarities for each sequence, with dots colored depending on the number of neighbors (light gray dots indicate a dense area, whereas
555 black dots a disperse area).

Figure 5 Dispersion plot of the CEM (Closest Environmental Match) and CCM (Closest Cultured Match) similarities for sequences affiliating to stramenopiles **(a)** and alveolates **(b)** separated in several taxonomic groups.

Figure 6 Heatmaps (left) and Venn diagrams (right) comparing the diversity of marine
560 picoeukaryotes among samples, using the shared or unique OTUs defined at clustering distances of 0.01 **(a)** or 0.20 **(b)**. Samples derive from the coast (1), offshore surface (31, 58 and 70) or offshore DCM (33, 60 and 72).

a

b

a

Clustering at 0.01 distance

b

Clustering at 0.20 distance

Table 1 Observed and estimated number of OTUs defined at discrete clustering levels (based on JC and patristic distances) within the 500 sequences of picoeukaryotes from the Indian Ocean. The estimated number of OTUs was calculated under several parametric and nonparametric models, showing the estimated value (**bold**), the standard error (*italics*) and the best fitting model (SE: Single Exponential; ME: Two Mixed Exponential; AC: ACE; A1: ACE1).

Distance	JC - distance grouping							Patristic distance grouping						
	Observed	Parametric estimate			Nonparametric estimate			Observed	Parametric estimate			Nonparametric estimate		
0.00	398	1951	<i>193</i>	SE	1320	<i>162</i>	AC							
0.01	237	731	<i>150</i>	ME	609	<i>91</i>	A1	242	803	<i>188</i>	ME	700	<i>117</i>	A1
0.02	197	624	<i>160</i>	ME	552	<i>96</i>	A1	205	617	<i>120</i>	ME	646	<i>122</i>	A1
0.03	173	472	<i>116</i>	ME	396	<i>64</i>	A1	186	710	<i>311</i>	ME	685	<i>155</i>	A1
0.04	149	312	<i>45</i>	ME	243	<i>25</i>	AC	170	557	<i>175</i>	ME	440	<i>79</i>	A1
0.05	134	251	<i>34</i>	ME	203	<i>19</i>	AC	158	486	<i>151</i>	ME	394	<i>73</i>	A1
0.07	117	224	<i>33</i>	ME	176	<i>18</i>	AC	135	357	<i>84</i>	ME	306	<i>56</i>	A1
0.10	94	158	<i>21</i>	ME	129	<i>12</i>	AC	121	257	<i>49</i>	ME	223	<i>35</i>	A1
0.12	78	147	<i>26</i>	ME	132	<i>24</i>	A1	113	231	<i>37</i>	ME	177	<i>20</i>	AC
0.15	58	91	<i>15</i>	ME	77	<i>9</i>	A1	99	184	<i>22</i>	ME	151	<i>18</i>	AC
0.20	39	61	<i>14</i>	ME	61	<i>15</i>	A1	82	159	<i>25</i>	ME	151	<i>29</i>	A1
0.30	20	27	<i>4</i>	SE	35	<i>14</i>	A1	47	85	<i>16</i>	ME	93	<i>26</i>	A1